

The benthic dinoflagellate genus *Prorocentrum* in five countries of Oceania

Diarrhetic shellfish toxin (DST) production has previously been found in benthic dinoflagellate species from the genus *Prorocentrum* and in planktonic dinoflagellate species from the genus *Dinophysis*. Details of the relationships between *Prorocentrum* species and their toxin production have not been fully elucidated in regions within Oceania. In this study, samples from five countries across Oceania (excluding Aotearoa New Zealand and the Rangitāhua Kermadec Islands; see [1]) were investigated.

Macroalgal (e.g., *Halimeda* spp. and *Padina* spp.) and seagrass (e.g., *Zostera* spp.) samples or epiphytes removed from the surface of macroalgae were collected into clear Ziplock bags, collection tubes, or plastic bottles by

hand and while snorkelling at sites in tropical/subtropical shallow coastal waters (<5 m depth) in 2003, 2014, 2018, and 2019 (Figs. 1 and 2): three sites in the Federated States of Micronesia, two sites in the Solomon Islands [2], one site in Niue [3], one site in the Cook Islands [4], and three sites in Australia [5–6]. Sample preparation procedures and the establishment of clonal isolates followed the methods described previously [1, 5–6]. Briefly, the isolates were maintained in sterile f/2–Si medium at 19 °C (for Australian strain SM43) or sterile metals mix SWII medium at 25 °C (± 2 °C) (for the other strains) under cool-white tube lights emitting approximately 60–90 μmol photons/m²/s with a photoperiod of 12:12 h (L:D).

Genetic experiments, including genomic DNA extraction, PCR of the large subunit ribosomal DNA (LSU rDNA) D1–D3 region, purification of the PCR amplicons, and sequencing for the established strains (except for the Australian strain SM43), were carried out according to the method described previously [1]. The experiments for strain SM43 followed the method described previously [5]. The sequences were aligned with reference sequences obtained from the DDBJ/EMBL/GenBank databases, and molecular phylogenetic analyses were performed using neighbour-joining (NJ) and maximum likelihood (ML) methods, as described previously [1]. The clade/subclade names of *P. lima* complex and *P. caipirignum*, as well as the rule for separating subclades based on at least one base pair change, which show different okadaic acid (OA) and dinophysistoxin-1 (DTX1) production characteristics, were used following a previous study [7].

Fig. 1. Sampling sites in this study. (A). Paiete Marine Park, Pohnpei, the Federated States of Micronesia. (B). Honiara, Guadalcanal Island, the Solomon Islands. (C). Titikaveka Beach, Rarotonga, the Cook Islands.

Fig. 2. Sampling and distribution map of 30 strains belonging to six benthic *Prorocentrum* species in five countries of Oceania. The numbers in each pie chart indicate the total number of clonal strains identified by molecular genetic methods. MPNi: Niho Marine Park, Pohnpei (6.943162, 158.169298). MPC: Paiete Marine Park, Pohnpei (6.982336, 158.200055). MPNe: Nett Point, Pohnpei (6.977970, 158.224998). B2RTH: Kinugawa Maru World War II ship wreck, Guadalcanal Island (−9.378672, 159.870754). NPHLB: Honiara, Guadalcanal Island (−9.430440, 159.991568). NMA: Avatele Beach, Makaapiapi (−19.126694, −169.913694). CIR: Titikaveka Beach, Rarotonga (−21.273333, −159.748056). RI: Raine Island, Queensland (−11.5903, 144.0350). HI: Heron Island, Queensland (−23.4423, 151.9148). MER: Merimbula, New South Wales (−36.8979, 149.9044).

DST analysis of all established strains, excluding strain SM43, cultured under the above conditions and harvested after approximately 50 days, was conducted for the ‘free’ and ‘total’ content of DSTs [OA, DTX1, and dinophysistoxin-2 (DTX2)] using liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry. The ‘esterified’ DST content was calculated by subtracting the ‘free’ content from the ‘total’ content. Details of the analysis have been described previously [1]. There was only ‘total’ DST content data available for strain SM43, which was cultured under the above conditions, harvested after approximately 20 days and analysed using the method outlined previously [8].

The Federated States of Micronesia: Eighteen benthic *Prorocentrum* strains were isolated from three sites, all within a kilometre of each other (MPNi, MPC, and MPNe), in 2018 (Fig. 1). They belonged to *P. lima* complex subclades 1a [number of strains (n) = 7], 1j (n = 4), and 1k (n = 3), *P. concavum* (n = 1), *P. cf. emarginatum* (n = 2), and *P. rathymum* (n = 1) (Figs. 2–3). Strains of *P. lima* complex subclade 1k

were established for the first time, and its subclade name is proposed in the present study (Fig. 3). The DST analysis revealed that the strains of *P. lima* complex subclades 1a, 1j, and 1k produced OA in the absence of DTX1 and DTX2. An isomer of DTX1 was detected as a very minor component in the strains of subclades 1a and 1k, but not in those of subclade 1j. The total DST cell quota of *P. lima* complex subclade 1a strains (19–44 pg/cell; total OA: 19–44 pg/cell; total DTX1 isomer: 0.093–0.16 pg/cell) tended to be higher than that of *P. lima* complex subclades 1j (14–19 pg/cell; total OA: 14–19 pg/cell) and 1k strains (19–22 pg/cell; total OA: 18–21 pg/cell; total DTX1 isomer: 0.66–0.84 pg/cell) (Fig. 4). All strains of *P. concavum*, *P. cf. emarginatum*, and *P. rathymum* did not produce any of the tested DSTs. To the best of our knowledge, this study is the first report of the benthic *Prorocentrum* species in the Federated States of Micronesia.

The Solomon Islands: Four benthic *Prorocentrum* strains were isolated from two sites in 2018 (Fig. 1), and their sequences have been reported previ-

ously [2]. All strains belonged to *P. lima* complex subclade 1a (Figs. 2 and 3). These strains mainly produced OA, with DTX1 and the DTX1 isomer as minor components (total DSTs: 15–17 pg/cell; total OA: 11–15 pg/cell; total DTX1: 0.25–1.8 pg/cell; total DTX1 isomer: 0–2.6 pg/cell), in the absence of DTX2 (Fig. 4). Currently, the only recorded species in the Solomon Islands belongs to the *P. lima* complex.

Niue: Strains of benthic *Prorocentrum* isolated from a single site in 2018 were previously reported as *P. hoffmannianum*, identified by sequencing [3]. The present study reconfirmed the previous identification with phylogenetic analyses, showing that four strains belonged to that species, and revealed that they produced OA in the absence of DTX1, DTX1 isomer, and DTX2 (total OA: 13–25 pg/cell) (Figs. 2–4). Currently, the only recorded species in Niue is *P. hoffmannianum*.

The Cook Islands: One benthic *Prorocentrum* strain isolated from a single site in 2019 (Fig. 1) belonged to *P. concavum* and did not produce any tested DSTs (Figs. 2–3). Previously, two species (*P. lima* complex and *P. cf. maculosum*) have been reported based on morphological observations [9]. Therefore, the present study is the first record of *P. concavum* from the Cook Islands.

Australia: One benthic *Prorocentrum* strain isolated from Raine Island, Queensland in 2003 belonged to the *P. caipirignum* subclade b and produced OA without DTX1, the DTX1 isomer, or DTX2 (total OA: 51 pg/cell) (Figs. 2–4). Two strains isolated from Heron Island, Queensland and Merimbula, New South Wales in 2014 belonged to the *P. lima* complex subclade 1d and produced OA, with the DTX1 isomer as a very minor component, in the absence of DTX1 and DTX2 (total DSTs: 8.8–11 pg/cell; total OA: 8.8–11 pg/cell; total DTX1 isomer: 0.030–0.045 pg/cell) (Figs. 2–4). Previously, seven species (*P. clipeus*, *P. concavum*, *P. fukuyoi*, *P. hoffmannianum*, *P. lima* complex, *P. malayense*,

Fig. 3. Molecular phylogenetic tree of the benthic *Prorocentrum* species based on the LSU rDNA D1–D2 sequences (37 sequences, 657 positions) using the neighbour-joining (NJ) method. Strains in this study are shown in black and bold fonts. The analysis was conducted using the best DNA models, TN93 + G for NJ and TN93 + G + I for ML methods. Nodal support represents the NJ bootstrap value/maximum likelihood (ML) bootstrap value. Nodal support under 50 in NJ/ML is shown as a hyphen (-). A node that was not present in the ML tree is labelled as np. *1–5: Identical sequence(s) in each species or subclade. *6: Sequence determined previously [2]. *: Sequence determined in the present study but not registered. *8: Subclade proposed in the present study.

Fig. 4. Diarrhetic shellfish toxin (DST) profiles of the benthic *Prochlorocentrum* strains. (A). DST cell quota (pg/cell). (B). DST proportion (%). *1: A strain analysed for only total DSTs.

and *P. rhathymum*) were reported from Australia [10–11]. To the best of our knowledge, the present study is the first record of *P. caipirignum* from this country.

In conclusion, among the strains investigated in the present study, only strains belonging to the *P. lima* complex, *P. caipirignum*, and *P. hoffmannianum* were found to produce OA, DTX1, and/or DTX1 isomer, with varying toxin cell quotas. The DST cell quotas of a *P. caipirignum* subclade b strain from Australia and *P. lima* complex subclade 1a strains from the Federated States of Micronesia tended to be higher than those of the other strains of the *P. lima* complex and *P. hoffmannianum* from the other investigated locations. There are, therefore, potential risks to seafood safety caused by these DST-producing species in the investigated areas. Although the present study reported six benthic *Prochlorocentrum* species from these areas, the sampling effort was limited, and the number of established strains was small. It is, therefore, necessary to conduct further investigations into the diversity and toxin production of benthic *Prochlorocentrum* species to develop more robust baseline data and

to assess whether they pose a seafood safety risk in these areas.

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